

Effect of Green Entrepreneurship Practices on the Performance of Poultry-Based Enterprises in Abia State, Nigeria.

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Abstract: The study evaluated the effect of green entrepreneurship practices on the performance of poultry-based enterprises in Abia State, Nigeria. The objectives of the study were to: describe the socio-economic characteristics, assess the level of involvement in green entrepreneurship among poultry-based enterprises, evaluate the cost of adoption/use of green entrepreneurship, and determine the effect of green entrepreneurship on poultry-based enterprises performance. A purposive sampling technique was used in this study to select 120 poultry entrepreneurs practicing green entrepreneurship. Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire and personal interviews. Statistical tools such as Mean, Percentage, Frequency distribution, and Ordinary Least squares (OLS) regression were used in analyzing the data generated. The result showed that the majority (72.5%) of the respondents involved in the practice of green entrepreneurship were young, energetic, and enterprising with greater drive and passion for financial freedom through the adoption of sustainable, eco-friendly practices. In addition, most (65%) of the respondents were male, literate (95%), having a large family size (85%), with essential experience for practicing green entrepreneurship. In addition, the result showed that there is a high level of involvement in pollution control (75%) and recycling/ reuse (85%) while the involvement level of respondents in solar energy use was 33% and could be said to be low since it is less than 50%. However, the overall average cost of adopting green entrepreneurship was ₦ 68913.67. This means that respondents can practice green entrepreneurship if they can save ₦ 5743.00 per month from their business returns. In addition, the result shows that there is a positive and significant 5% relationship between recycling/reuse of poultry waste and by-products and poultry enterprise performance. It is recommended that the young, literate, and experienced individuals should be supported with the right tools/inputs/financial resources to be able to properly adopt green entrepreneurship practices especially recycling/reuse of waste/by-products of poultry products.

Keywords: *Green entrepreneurship, Practices, Performance, Poultry, Enterprise*

Introduction

Green Entrepreneurship initiative is a practice of an entrepreneur that refers to all the related projects with a specific aim of helping businesses reduce the environmental impacts of their business operations as well as helping them to save money. This means that they will use fewer raw materials, less natural resources, less energy, and less water, which will lead to producing less waste and less cost of running the business. The concept of green entrepreneurship evolved because of environmental concerns such as pollution, global warming, climate change, and scarcity of natural resources, which constitute strategic environmental concerns to stakeholders in business (Ataman *et al.*, 2018; Sharma & Kushwaha, 2013; Enoh *et al.*, 2020).

According to Bakari (2013), green entrepreneurs create social value and business models for environmental and economic profitability. This results in green business with less adverse impact on the environment both globally and locally, and it requires principles of sustainability in all business decisions to have a friendly environment for products and services (Gevrenova, 2015). Similarly, Huang (2010) opines that green entrepreneurship helps to address social and

environmental needs using entrepreneurial ideas to assess the level of risk, financial sustainability, and the effect of environmental challenges on the natural environment. In the same vein, Bakari (2013) and Schapper (2016) note that the practices of green entrepreneurs are aimed at recycling, reducing, and reusing resources for the sustainability of the environment and economy. This requires actions directed at preventing waste, pollution, and energy saving. Hence, green entrepreneurs are innovative solution providers of goods and services produced and consumed based on business models that contribute to a greener economy (Demuth, 2015; Hossam, 2015).

On the other hand, business performance entails the outcome of business activities with the state of efficiency and productivity. It may be financial performance concerning growth, profitability etc, or non-financial performance with customer satisfaction, internal processes, efficiency, etc. Therefore, improved performance as a requirement for an organization's success is measured to determine the extent of the organization's achievement of set goals and objectives (Makanga and Paul, 2017; Eniola and Ektebang, 2014). In green entrepreneurship, business performance consists of operational and competitive performance, either in the

manufacturing or service industry which are aimed at optimizing growth, expansion, and profitability for the stakeholders as organizations strategically engage in the short and long-term goals of the organization.

This study therefore, evaluated the effect of green entrepreneurship practices on the performance of poultry-based enterprises in Abia State. The specific objectives are to determine the socio-economic characteristics of respondents involved in green entrepreneurship, assess the level of involvement in green entrepreneurship (recycling, pollution control, and solar energy use) among poultry-based enterprises, evaluate the cost of adoption/use of green entrepreneurship, and determine the effect of green entrepreneurship on agro enterprises performance.

Methodology

This study was carried out in Abia State which is in the southeastern part of Nigeria, the capital is Umuahia. Abia State occupies about 6,320 square kilometers and is bounded on the north and northeast by the States of Anambra, Enugu, and Ebonyi. To the west of Abia is Imo State, to the east and southeast are Cross River State and Akwa Ibom State, respectively, and to the south is Rivers State.

The population of the study consists of 47767 poultry farmers (NBS/FMARD, Report). First, Abia State has 17 LGAs, and 6 LGAs were randomly selected for analysis. Second, from each of the selected LGAs, 20 poultry farmers were randomly selected from each of the selected LGAs ensuring a more representative sample and helped mitigate bias by ensuring that participants are selected based on chance rather than preconceived notions.

This gave a total sample size of 120 poultry farmers. Primary data were collected from the 120 respondents with the use of a well-structured questionnaire and complimented with an oral interview. Copies of the questionnaire were given to few experts for corrections and comments on the content of the questionnaire. To determine the reliability of the research instrument, a trial test of the instrument using 15 poultry farmers who were not part of the study were selected randomly and the study was conducted. The Cronbach Alpha reliability test was conducted for internal consistency of the instrument. The Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.75 shows the instrument is highly reliable. Statistical tools such as mean, percentage, and frequency distribution and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression were used in

analyzing the data generated. The implicit form of the regression model is stated as follows;

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3), \text{ Where,}$$

Y= Performance of poultry farmers measured in quantity of birds sold in naira

X₁= Amount spent on recycling/reuse measured in naira

X₂= Amount spent on pollution control measured in naira

X₃= Amount spent on solar/renewable energy measured in naira

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic characteristics of respondents involved in green entrepreneurship

Distribution based on the socio-economic characteristics of respondents involved in green entrepreneurship is presented in Table 1

Table 1: Distribution based on the socio-economic characteristics of respondents involved in green entrepreneurship

Socioeconomic characteristics			
Age	Frequency	Percent	Mean
21-30	45	37.5	
31-40	42	35.0	
41-50	27	22.5	
51-60	6	5.0	
Total	120	100	35.3
Sex			
Male	78	65.0	
Female	42	35.0	
Total	120	100	
Level of education			
No formal education	6	5.0	
Primary	3	2.2	
Secondary	21	17	
Tertiary	90	75.0	
Total	120	100.0	
Marital status			
Single	66	55	
Married	54	45	
Total	120	100	
Household size			
1-3	18	15	
4-6	84	70	
7-9	15	12.5	
10-12	3	2.5	
Total	120	100	5.3
Years of Experience			
1-10	100	83.3	
11-20	17	14.2	
21-30	3	2.5	
Total	120	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 show that 72.5% of the respondents had ages ranging between 21-40 years. The mean age of the respondents was 35. This indicates that the majority of the respondents involved in eco-friendly practices were young, energetic, and enterprising. Being young, energetic, and enterprising could mean greater drive and passion for financial freedom through a sustainable eco-friendly practice.

More so, Table 1 shows that 65% of the respondents selected for the study were male while 35% were female. This means that the majority of the respondents were males. The high incidence of males in the study could be that males are the breadwinners of their homes and are regularly confronted with the management of poultry-based waste products to the advantage of the poultry enterprise without compromising the eco-standards.

Table 1 shows that 95% of the respondents involved in green entrepreneurship had one form of education or another. This means that the majority of the respondents are literate. Being literate could mean greater skill in handling eco-friendly practices and ideas effectively. Education is a vital quality for enterprise owners, as it gives them the ability

to access useful technologies and information, as well as acquire new skills to develop their on- and off-farm activities that can improve their livelihoods (Ogbe, 2023).

Table 1 show that 85% of the respondents had household sizes ranging between 1-6. The mean of 5 persons. This means that most of the respondents involved in poultry production had a large family size. This scenario implies that respondents had access to family labour which is useful in sourcing eco-friendly technologies and information.

Table 1 shows that 96% of the respondents had years of experience ranging between 1-10 years. The mean years of experience was about 5 years indicating that most of the respondents were experienced individuals in poultry enterprise. Experience means that the respondents had practical knowledge of poultry enterprises and could have developed a pathway of managing poultry waste for the benefit of the enterprise and environment.

Level of Involvement in Green Entrepreneurship Practices

The level of involvement in green entrepreneurship practices among the respondents is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Level of involvement in green entrepreneurship practices

s/n	Green entrepreneurship practices	Frequency	Percent
Pollution control			
1	Regular cleaning/clearing of drainage	80	66.7**
2	Burying of waste	72	60**
3	Burning of waste inside incinerator	75	62.5**
4	Drying and bagging of waste	73	60.8**
5	Storing liquid waste in septic tank	75	62.5**
	Total	375	75**
Solar energy use			
1	Use of solar inverters and panel	25	20.8*
2	Use of energy bulbs	44	36.7*
3	Use of solar energy security lights	30	25*
	Total	99	33*
Recycling/reuse			
1	Use of waste in vegetable farm	120	100**
2	Use of waste in generating maggot for feed inclusion	90	75**
3	Use of waste in feeding pigs	45	37.5*
	Total	255	85**

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents had a high level of involvement in pollution control and recycling/ reuse with the mean involvement level of 75% and 85% respectively. The high incidence of involvement of respondents in pollution control and recycling could be associated with the growing concern for the environment and a heightened awareness of the need for sustainable practices. Faster capital (2024) enumerated the environmental concerns to climate change, pollution, and resource depletion which have become pressing issues

in developed and developing economies that demand immediate attention.

Lastly, the involvement level of respondents in solar energy use was 33%. This could be said to be low since it is less than 50%. This result could be associated with the relatively high cost associated with solar energy procurement and setup.

Cost of adopting green entrepreneurship practices

Cost of adopting green entrepreneurship practices among the respondents is presented in Table 3

Table 3: Cost of adopting green entrepreneurship practices among the respondents

Green entrepreneurship practices	Mean cost (Naira)	Ranking on cost	Ease of adoption
Pollution control	73680	2 nd	2 nd
Solar energy use	103181	1 st	3 rd
Recycling/reuse	29880	3 rd	1 st
Average	68913.67		

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 3 shows that the cost of adopting solar energy use came top among the respondents with a mean cost of ₦ 103181.00. This is followed by pollution control with the mean cost of adoption of ₦ 73680.00. Lastly, the mean cost of adopting recycling/reuse by the respondents was ₦ 29880.00. Furthermore, the ease of adopting recycling/reuse of poultry-based waste and other associated materials was higher with less associated cost (₦ 29880.00) than pollution control (₦ 73680.00) and solar energy use (₦ 103181.00). The adoption of recycling/reuse of poultry-based waste and other associated materials may be due to the smallness of financial involvement and minimum training/skill for its adoption and practice. In addition,

the ease of adopting pollution control was next in line with varying reasons ranging from the suitability of the business environment as attractants for potential business clients to less financial involvement in the health of the business operators. The overall average cost of adopting green entrepreneurship was ₦ 68913.67. This means that respondents can practice green entrepreneurship if they can save ₦5743.00 per month from their business returns.

Effect of Green entrepreneurship practices on poultry-based enterprise performance.

Effect of green entrepreneurship practices on poultry-based enterprise performance is presented in Table 4

Table 4: Effect of green entrepreneurship practices on poultry-based enterprise performance.

Variables	Coefficient	Standard error	T value
Constant	89658.249	181152.41	0.495 ^{ns}
Pollution control	9.142	11.977	0.763 ^{ns}
Solar energy use	7.883	6.665	1.183 ^{ns}
Recycling/Reuse	4.267	1.526	2.796 ^{**}
R ²	0.848		
R ⁻²	0.733		
F ratio	7.418 ^{***}		

Source: Field survey, 2021 ** Significant at 5% ns-not significant

Table 4 shows that there is a positive and significant (5%) relationship between the recycling/reuse of poultry waste and by products and poultry enterprise performance. This means that recycling/reuse increased, and performance also increased. The implication of recycling/reuse of waste poultry products could be associated with the little or no technical skill/training in its adoption. Pollution control had a positive but not significant relationship with the performance of poultry-based enterprises. This means that as pollution control increased, the performance also increased. The non-significance of pollution control could be associated with poor environmental consciousness. According to Egbu (2000), the environmental consciousness in the developed world has witnessed over the past two decades generally effective mechanisms for pollution abatement, the situation in many third-world nations including Nigeria is at best tepid. Solar energy had a positive but non-significant relationship with the performance of agroenterprise. This means that as solar energy use increased, performance also increased. Increased solar energy use could mean increased investment in clean energy and power supply. The more power supply, the more the effectiveness of poultry-based enterprise performance.

However, the non-significance of solar energy use could be associated with high adoption costs. Amadi *et al.* (2024) confirm that the upfront costs of solar panel systems, inverters, and batteries can be a significant barrier, particularly for low-income households and businesses. The R^2 (coefficient of multiple determination) was 0.848 signifying that 84.8% of the total variation observed in the performance (dependent variable) was accounted for by the independent variables included in the model. The F-value was 7.418 which is significant at 1% indicating that green entrepreneurship had an effects on the performance of poultry-based enterprises.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that individuals involved in the practice of green entrepreneurship were young males, young, literate with the required years of experience and passion for financial freedom through the adoption of sustainable eco-friendly practices. In addition, there was a high level of involvement of respondents in pollution control and recycling/ reuse. Furthermore, the study showed that the majority of the respondents can practice green entrepreneurship if they can save ₦ 5743.00 per month from their business returns. In addition, the result shows that there is a

positive and significant 5% relationship between recycling/reuse of poultry waste and by-products and poultry enterprise performance. Furthermore, 80%, 78%, and 76% of the respondents indicated that inadequate power supply, inadequate funding, and high cost of inputs/climate change as their main constraints to the adoption of green entrepreneurship practices. The study therefore recommends that young, literate, and experienced individuals should be supported with the right tools/inputs/financial resources to be able to properly adopt green

entrepreneurship practices especially recycling/reuse of waste poultry products. This measure would ensure that respondents operate their poultry business in a healthy environment while producing eco-friendly poultry-based produce that commands the right market price. More so, poultry-based entrepreneurs should be encouraged to save a proportion of their returns monthly to sustain the practice of green entrepreneurship.

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